

A Faster Convergence Technique for Solving α - k Search Problems in Monte Carlo Simulations using Iterated Fission Probability

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ABSTRACT

The ability to evaluate the governing asymptotic time-eigenvalue of the neutron transport equation, frequently referred to as the α -eigenvalue, is an increasingly important capability of Monte Carlo codes with regards to time-dependent analysis. This α -eigenvalue is an important quantity in the evaluation of many common transient phenomena, including: reactor start up and shut down analysis, measurements of the dynamic or static reactivity of a system, or propagation of a transport solution in time via quasi-static methods. The most common method in literature to determine the α -eigenvalue in Monte Carlo is called the α - k algorithm. This solution method was implemented into the open-source Monte Carlo code OpenMC, along with a new method for sampling α -based time-events. In addition, a method for more rapidly converging the search for the α -eigenvalue using kinetics parameters generated via the Iterated Fission Probability method was created. Generation of the initial α -eigenvalue guess is done in a quick k -eigenvalue run. The resulting kinetics parameters generated by the Iterated Fission Probability method are used with the inhour equation to solve for an approximate, governing exponential mode. It was found that improving the initial guess of the α - k algorithm with this method results in a reduction to the number of batches and total simulation time needed for convergence of the α -eigenvalue. Several benchmark problems were performed to demonstrate the effectiveness of this technique. To conclude, a number of recommendations were made for other ways in which this method might benefit α -eigenvalue problems, and situations in which the faster convergence was less beneficial were discussed.

Keywords: α -eigenvalue, Convergence, Time-Dependent, Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

Integration of α -eigenvalues into Monte Carlo (MC) requires a brief understanding of the α -eigenvalue formalism. The neutron transport equation (NTE) is recast by factorizing the time-dependent angular flux solution into a shape and amplitude component [1]. The amplitude component is expressed as an exponential function in time with governing mode α . The changes made to the neutron flux and delayed neutron precursor concentrations, or more succinctly precursors, can be seen in equations 1 and 2

$$\psi(r, E, \Omega, t) = \psi_\alpha(r, E, \Omega)e^{\alpha t}, \quad (1)$$

$$C_i(r, t) = C_i(r)e^{\alpha t}. \quad (2)$$

Where ψ is the complete angular flux solution, ψ_α is the shape eigenfunction for the α -eigenvalue formalism, C_i is the concentration for precursor family i , and α is the time-eigenvalue. A complete derivation for the fundamental mode α is beyond the scope of this analysis, but can be found readily in literature [2]. In brief, the separability of the neutron flux permits a spectra of time-eigenvalues; however, as $t \rightarrow \infty$, a dominant mode emerges. As higher-order time-modes decay away, the dominant mode becomes the governing exponential constant. With simple definitions for our time-derivatives

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for neutron flux and precursor concentration deduced through equations 1 and 2, the NTE used in solving α -eigenvalue problems through the class of algorithms known as α - k searches can be established by equation 3

$$\frac{\alpha}{v}\psi_{\alpha}(r, E, \Omega) + L\psi_{\alpha}(r, E, \Omega) = \frac{1}{k}Q\psi_{\alpha}(r, E, \Omega), \quad (3)$$

where L is the net loss operator given by

$$Lf = \hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla f + \Sigma_t(r, E)f - \int_{4\pi} \int_0^{\infty} v_s(E')\Sigma_s(r, \hat{\Omega}' \rightarrow \hat{\Omega}, E' \rightarrow E)fdE'd\Omega', \quad (4)$$

and Q is the fission source operator given by

$$Qf = \frac{1}{4\pi}\chi_p(E) \int_0^{\infty} v_p(r, E')\Sigma_f(r, E')fdE' + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\chi_{d,i}(E)}{4\pi} \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_i + \alpha} \int_0^{\infty} v_{d,i}(E')\Sigma_f(r, E')fdE'. \quad (5)$$

Nomenclature for equations 3 through 5 is defined by the following: v is the neutron velocity, Σ_t is the total macroscopic cross section, v_s is the scattering multiplicity term, Σ_s is the scattering macroscopic cross section, χ_p is the prompt fission spectrum, v_p is the average number of prompt fission neutrons released per fission, Σ_f is the fission macroscopic cross section, χ_d is the delayed neutron spectrum of precursor family i , λ_i is the precursor decay constant of family i , $v_{d,i}$ is the average number of delayed neutrons produced from fission of family i , and N is the total number of precursor families. Also note that k is a normalizing term for the fission source which comes from the k -eigenvalue formulation. In the better known k -eigenvalue calculations, the value of the k -eigenvalue is found by first guessing a fission source and then iterating until the fission source is converged. The value of k , which reflects the ratio of created to source particles, represents either an abundance or dearth of neutrons which must be corrected via normalization to keep the total weight of particles between cycles in MC the same.

In α - k search algorithms the numerical value of k is determined via consecutive generations similar to traditional k -eigenvalue problems, however, in this case it is used as a tuning parameter for the α -eigenvalue. In this way the value of k in the α - k algorithm no longer represents a true eigenvalue. The value of the α -eigenvalue itself must be handled in a unique manner altogether. Initially, a guess must be given to the α -eigenvalue of the system. The resulting α/v term then acts like an additional cross section to the simulation [2]. This value will be referred to as the α cross section, as it reflects the propensity for particles to undergo a so-called α -event. This event is a form of time-based population control, a method which controls the multiplying or decaying particle populations of nuclear systems [3]. In addition to α events, an energy spectral change can also be seen in equation 5 with the $\lambda_i/(\lambda_i + \alpha)$ term. The goal of the time-based population control of α -events is to eventually converge the k tuning value in equation 3 to unity. A k of unity represents no fission normalization, such that the control of consecutive generations is handled by α -events, and the fundamental time-eigenvalue is therefore obtained for our system.

For particles to undergo the time-based population control, the α/v term is added to the total macroscopic cross section. If α is positive, this population control takes the effect of an additional absorber in the system. Therefore, if a particle undergoes an α -event, it will be absorbed. If however α is negative, then the positivity of the total macroscopic cross section is not guaranteed. To circumvent this, it is common to add $2|\alpha|/v$ to equation 3 [2, 4]. This change mathematically creates a new (n, 2n) reaction with a cross section of $-\alpha/v$. The probability for this reaction to occur is only a function of the α value and the particles' velocity. Distributions in energy and angle for the outgoing particle are characterized by a Dirac δ distribution [5]. In most MC codes, the effects of this reaction can easily be achieved by multiplying the weight of the particle which undergoes this reaction by 2. Alternatively, storing a copy of the particle at the site where the α -event occurred, and simulating this new copy particle as part of the secondary event bank from the original particle, would have a similar effect.

The simplest way to update the value of α from cycle i to cycle $i + 1$, is to perform a linear bisection as a function of k [2]. If α is positive, this update takes the form of

$$\alpha_i k_i = \alpha_{i+1}, \quad (6)$$

or if α is negative

$$\frac{\alpha_i}{k_i} = \alpha_{i+1}. \quad (7)$$

There is a caveat to the update schemes presented in equations 6 and 7. The sign of the original guess of α (α_0) must be correct in order for the simulation to converge. Other update schemes exist which seek to solve this issue [4, 6], however they are far more involved to implement, and so will be left for future work. It is also important to note that in the form described in this section, the α - k search algorithm is highly sensitive to very negative α -eigenvalues. Some literature has attempted to improve upon this algorithm by stabilizing negative α searches [2, 7, 8]; however, the problems in this work will not attempt to solve systems requiring stabilization, so these methods will not be included. Instead, the focus of the OpenMC implementation in this work is centered on generating a highly accurate α_0 .

2. METHODS IN OPENMC

An implementation of the α - k search algorithm was integrated into the open-source Monte Carlo code OpenMC [9]. The majority of the implementation details, including the handling of the time-based population control and update scheme, are the same as the information covered in section 1. This section will discuss some of the novel techniques used in this version of the algorithm, and will cover the method used to generate an accurate α_0 value.

2.1. α -Event Handling in OpenMC

Typical implementations of the α - k search problem utilize a direct update to the total cross section to handle the time-based population control. This modification takes the form of

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_t = \Sigma_t + \frac{|\alpha|}{v}. \quad (8)$$

Equation 8 contains a modified total cross section, $\tilde{\Sigma}_t$, which possesses the information associated with the propensity to undergo an α -event. This information allows α -events to be sampled during regular particle transport. However, it should be noted that a direct change to the material properties oftentimes requires changes to other routines in order to keep the statistical simulation unbiased. In the case of OpenMC, a direct modification to the total cross section requires additional updates for tallying and for nuclide sampling. Rather than attempting to adapt the rest of the code for this new total cross section, an alternative idea was proposed. Instead of modifying material data, an α -event is sampled by computing its nearest probabilistic distance. Mathematically, this is similar to computing the nearest distance to collision, but uses the α cross section instead of the total cross section

$$x_\alpha = \frac{-\ln(\zeta)}{\frac{|\alpha|}{v}}. \quad (9)$$

Where ζ is a random number sampled on the unit interval, and therefore x_α is the distance to the nearest alpha event. This computed distance is then compared to the nearest distance to surface intersection and distance to collision. The minimum of the three distances is selected as the event-type, and if an α -event is selected, the time-based population control will take effect. This method prevents the need to directly modify the total cross section by introducing a new event-type, and prevented the need to change any additional OpenMC routines.

2.2. Generating Initial Guesses with Iterated Fission Probability

One of the long-standing issues with the α - k search algorithm, is that it can take many particles and latent generations within a cycle to accurately converge to the correct α -eigenvalue [2]. The order of magnitude of α -eigenvalues varies greatly from being on the order of inverse-seconds to inverse-microseconds [10] depending on the problem configuration and neutron energy spectra. It is for this reason that an analysis was conducted to attempt to generate accurate guesses to the value of α_0 . Recent work in OpenMC on the Iterated Fission Probability (IFP) method was considered for this task [11]. The IFP method, which solves the adjoint NTE, is frequently used to generate adjoint weighted kinetics parameters [12]. It was proposed that by generating a set of kinetics parameters via IFP, it would be possible to then solve the inhour equation of point-kinetics. The solution to this equation, given a one-group precursor model, yields two time-modes. One of these modes can then be used as an input guess to the initial value of α in an α - k simulation. This idea was in part motivated by the fact that the Rossi- α , also known as the prompt decay mode [13], has been shown to generate a good answer to the alpha-eigenvalue for prompt-subcritical/delayed-critical experiments [2, 10]. If the initial guess for α_0 can at least get the order of magnitude correct, it should speed up the convergence of the α - k iterations without requiring prior knowledge by the code user. To compute the modes in OpenMC via IFP, the following equations were used with the assumption of a one-group precursor model

$$\alpha\Lambda - (\rho - \beta) = \lambda_b \frac{\beta}{\lambda_b + \alpha}, \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha^2 - \alpha\left(\frac{\rho - \beta}{\Lambda} - \lambda_b\right) - \lambda_b \frac{\rho}{\Lambda} = 0. \quad (11)$$

Where Λ is the mean generation time, ρ is the static reactivity, β is the effective delayed neutron fraction, and λ_b is the inverse beta-weighted decay constant over all precursor families. Equation 11 shows the inhour equation with one effective precursor family in quadratic form. This form may be solved trivially to yield two roots, the more positive of the two representing the guess α_0 for the α - k algorithm. Λ and β are computed with tally results from IFP in OpenMC, ρ is computed by taking the definition of static reactivity after a k -eigenvalue run $(k - 1)/k$, and λ_b is computed during this run by inverse-beta weighting of the precursor families' decay constants in combination with atomic weighting of the fissionable nuclides. It should be noted that because this methodology uses point-kinetics, it is expected that the alpha-modes computed in equation 11 will only be highly accurate for problems close to $k = 1$, or problems which have little to no spatial effects. Despite these inaccuracies, the potential for faster convergence should still exist in problems where k is far from 1.

3. TEST PROBLEMS

In order to determine the ability to gain more rapid convergence of α - k search algorithms using the initial guess computed via section 2.2, a set of three test problems have been conducted. The first two of these test problems are part of the well-known suite of high-enriched uranium (HEU) sphere benchmarks by Cullen [14]. Cullen I and Cullen II were chosen due to their differences in criticality, and their frequent use in literature as a benchmark [2, 4, 5]. These problems represent a prompt sub-critical/delayed critical and prompt supercritical configuration of the Godiva sphere respectively. The final problem chosen was configured to resemble a system that a user might simulate when analyzing a nuclear reactor. A 17×17 pressurized water reactor (PWR) assembly was configured with a set of gadolium burnable absorber pins in the configuration. Unlike the Cullen problems which contain vacuum boundary conditions, this PWR assembly is reflective. The 17×17 PWR assembly is over-enriched, and is expected to have a k -eigenvalue well above unity. Due to this deviation from $k = 1$, and the spatial effects of the burnable absorbers, it is thought that the α_0 from the k -eigenvalue run for the assembly will be less exact than the result of Cullen I. It is also expected that the order-of-magnitude of

the PWR assembly's α -eigenvalue will be different to Cullen's sphere problems. A 2-dimensional slice of the PWR assembly can be seen in Figure 1. Before any tests on α - k convergence could take place,

Figure 1. 2D slice of the 17×17 PWR assembly used to test α - k convergence.

k -eigenvalue and α - k runs were done to obtain a set of expected values. For the k -eigenvalue runs, 10 inactive and 50 active cycles were run with a set of 10,000 particles per-cycle. For the initial α - k simulations, 1000 cycles of 10,000 particles were run, with four latent generations per cycle. The initial α_0 value was set to either $1s^{-1}$ or $-1s^{-1}$ depending on the multiplicity of the system. This unit-guess for α_0 was chosen to represent a logical choice for users who might be unfamiliar with the specific time-dynamics of their simulated system. The tests were run in prompt-only mode to compare to existing literature which runs the Cullen benchmarks with only prompt neutrons [2, 4, 5]. A summary of the results for k -eigenvalue and α - k runs, with the IFP generated α_0 value from the k -eigenvalue run, can be found in Table I. The results of these runs display the expected behavior of generating α_0 with IFP. Cullen I

Table I. Results of initial runs for the sample tests.

Benchmark	k -eigenvalue	α_0 via IFP [s^{-1}]	α -eigenvalue [s^{-1}]
Cullen I	0.9930 ± 0.00121	$(-1.136 \pm 0.038) \times 10^6$	$(-1.169 \pm 0.032) \times 10^6$
Cullen II	1.5863 ± 0.00157	$(74.103 \pm 0.2318) \times 10^6$	$(146.06 \pm 0.157) \times 10^6$
17×17 Assembly	1.1168 ± 0.00184	$(7.606 \pm 0.011) \times 10^3$	$(8.808 \pm 0.0319) \times 10^3$

shows near identical agreement between the converged α - k iteration and the guess generated from the k -eigenvalue run. Cullen II shows the greatest discrepancy between the values of α due to its far-from-critical nature. Finally, the 17×17 PWR assembly shows an approximate 15% difference between the two values of α . The following analysis will seek to quantify the faster convergence achieved by using the α_0 value generated via IFP as an initial guess for α - k iterations.

4. CONVERGENCE RESULTS

To determine the difference in convergence by using a more accurate α_0 , a metric called time-to-convergence (TTC) was analyzed. This analysis defines TTC as the time from the beginning of the simulation until a cycle during α - k iterations successfully begins oscillating about the correct α -eigenvalue. This correct α is super-imposed during the simulation as a known quantity depending on the benchmark. A timer was added to OpenMC which begins during loading of the initial α_0 guess, and ends when convergence has been determined. Each benchmark will be run with α_0 being either: obtained from IFP with one latent generation per cycle, a unit-guess with one latent generation per cycle, or a unit-guess with 4 latent generations per cycle. Figure 2 shows the visual convergence of α as a function of batch number for the different runs of the Cullen I problem. Note that the dashed red line indicates the expectation value of a converged α -eigenvalue for this benchmark. The results from Figure 2 show that the α_0 guess generated from IFP is a substantially better starting point for the α - k iterations than a unit guess. This

Figure 2. α convergence as a function of batch for the Cullen I test.

was expected since the Rossi- α , which is computed by the inhour equation when no delayed neutrons are present, is already known to very well approximate the α -eigenvalue of prompt subcritical/delayed critical experiments [13, 2]. A unit guess for this type of benchmark is a very poor choice as the α - k iterations do not sufficiently change the initial value of α_0 per-iteration. For any convergence to be achieved in Cullen I from a unit guess, multiple latent generations must be run. Figures 3 and 4 show the visual convergence of the Cullen II problem and 17×17 PWR lattice respectively. The results in figures 3 and

Figure 3. α convergence as a function of batch for the Cullen II test.

4 show less rapid convergence than in figure 2. As the k -eigenvalue deviates further from 1, the α - k iterations do a better job at more rapidly converging the α -eigenvalue. The curve which represents the unit guess of α_0 run with 4 latent generations is able to closely compete with the guess from IFP. Despite this fact, the α_0 generated by IFP converges much faster than the curve representative of only one latent generation per batch with a unit-guess. What this result indicates is that, from a TTC perspective, the α_0 from IFP should converge faster than a unit guess. TTC results were collected in Table II. Note that the second column of Table II includes the cost of running the k -eigenvalue calculation to generate the α_0 from IFP. While it is common to run a k -eigenvalue calculation before any time-dependent analysis [2], the cost was only included for α_0 from IFP, as it is mandatory in this case. Table II confirms the core hypothesis of this analysis, and shows between approximately 18 and 5 times speedups for the TTC with α_0 generated by IFP in comparison to the unit guesses. When the computational cost in time is considered for generating the α_0 value via IFP, the speedups reduce to approximately 8 and 2 times for the Cullen I and 17×17 PWR Assembly tests respectively. For the Cullen II benchmark, we see a reduc-

Figure 4. α convergence as a function of batch for the 17×17 PWR lattice test.

Table II. TTC results for the tests problems for different α_0 .

Benchmark	IFP α_0 [s]	IFP α_0 with k [s]	Unit α_0 [s]	Unit α_0 : 4 gen [s]
Cullen I	0.52	1.23	Did not converge	9.39
Cullen II	0.04	0.87	0.21	0.23
17×17 Assembly	2.23	5.37	12.04	12.54

tion in computational speed due to requiring the k -eigenvalue run; however, it is important to re-iterate that a k -eigenvalue calculation is often run regardless of guess of α_0 . Factoring out this k -eigenvalue cost confirms speedups in all cases.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The α - k iterative algorithm was made faster in its convergence on the fundamental α -eigenvalue by generating an α_0 value from IFP during k -eigenvalue runs. This value is computed by injecting kinetics parameters generated by IFP into the single precursor group inhour equation. A set of problems were tested for the potential speedup of this method, and the total TTC was reduced across all cases. Inclusion of the time necessary to generate the α_0 from a k -eigenvalue run still gave noticeably faster convergence in all cases besides the Cullen II problem, which converged rapidly on its own due to a large deviation from criticality. Despite this result, given that k -eigenvalue runs are frequently performed before α - k iterations, the method of generating α_0 through IFP has potential benefits in all cases. Future analysis of this method will include: problems configured with delayed neutrons, improved update schemes for α - k iterations, and problems with larger, negative reactivity. This technique may also allow methods such as Generalized-IFP [15] to begin computation faster, since these methods rely on the convergence of an accurate α -eigenvalue in order to begin the calculation of generalized adjoint-weighted quantities.

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